

HITCHES AND PROSPECTS OF PHYSICAL DEVELOPMENT CONTROL ENFORCEMENT ON REAL ESTATE PLANNING, DEVELOPMENT, AND MANAGEMENT IN NASARAWA TOWN, NIGERIA

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Abstract

This paper examines the hitches and prospects of physical development control enforcement on real estate planning development and management in Nasarawa town, Nigeria. The purpose is to improve environmental quality, improved housing conditions, drainages, free flow of air among others. Despite the importance of development control measures in improving land use and management practices, there are series of factors that still negate its effectiveness which this paper seeks to address. The data for this study was obtained through a field survey, questionnaire, interview, Likert scale, and documentary materials. Thus a total of 431 household heads in rented and owner-occupation were randomly served with questionnaires. The data collected were analyzed by the use of percentages and tables with inferences. The paper revealed the following challenges of physical development control enforcement; Infiltration of corrupt and compromising officers, Absence of public enlightenment, inadequate enforcement of development control, haphazard physical development recorded in many places. Among other recommendations includes the need for adequate enforcement of laws and regulations, public enlightenment, and sanction of corrupt officers and besides these, the laws that will satisfy both private and public needs have to be harmonized into the present conditions in the building industry. For areas where reasonable success had been achieved the need to sustain the tempo and maintain the standard remains as the challenging factor. Thus for land use management to flourish and create a convenient and conducive environment for the present and future generations, there is a need for effective land use control enforcement mechanism, policy and action, and new legislation that will reflect best global practices.

Keywords: Physical Development Control, Enforcement, Real Estate Planning

I. Introduction

The housing policies of 1991 which was later modified in 2002, sought to guarantee access of all Nigerians to a decent, safe, and sanitary housing accommodation at a reasonable cost. This was to be realized through private sector initiative and partnership with the government and also through the provisions of urban and regional planning law of 1992, which seeks to reorganize physical planning in Nigeria (Aluko, 2000).

The growing hitches of unguided land use have attracted attention, both locally and internationally (Owoeye, 2020, Kimani, 2013).

Gateri (2002) established that *development control is a mechanism put in place to maintain standards thus reducing the negative effect that accompanies physical development. The mechanisms are in the form of policies, rules and laws put in place by the constituted authority to maintain standards towards reducing the negative influence of land use.*

In sub-Saharan African countries, cities have been found to continue to grow haphazardly in an uncontrolled manner (Alabi, 2010; Ache, 2019; Ifesanya, 2012). This has made planning policies and enforcement difficult and is most noticeable in the study area.

The Study Area

Nasarawa Local Government Council was created in 1976. The Nasarawa town is located in Nasarawa state, it lays between longitude 3 and 14 easts of the meridian and latitude 4 and 14, and is situated at the confluence of River Haderi and River Kurafe. The main access to Nasarawa is from Keffi and through Toto road which continues to Abaji. The road from Keffi branches off to the left and continues through Nasarawa towards Loko, Nasarawa town has several regional facilities such as the Federal Polytechnic Nasarawa, Government College. Government Science School, Government Day Secondary School, Community Secondary School, Local government secretariat, State ministry of land and survey, Nasarawa Urban development Board, Veterinary Office and Farm institutes, Federal road safety Office, Federal Civil Defense corps station, Police stations, Ministry of Works and housing, etc, Nasarawa local government area is located in Nasarawa State which lay within the central part of the entity called Nigeria. It covers an area of about 1,300 square kilometres with a population of 56,122 by 2006 population figure and an estimated population of 72,143 by 2021 using the Nasarawa state yearly population growth rate of 2.83%. Nasarawa Local Government shares a boundary with Keffi Local Government in the north, Kokona, and Doma in the east, Toto in the south, and Karu Local Government in the west. Nasarawa is 39 kilometres away from Keffi and 92 kilometres from Abuja. It is 159km away from the state headquarters Lafia.

Aim and Objectives.

This study aims to assess the problem of development control enforcement on real estate development and management in Nasarawa, Nasarawa State, Nigeria.

The major objective of this work is to assess development control enforcement and its challenges on real estate development and management in Nigeria.

II. The Theoretical Background

The Nigeria town and country planning law of 1992 defines development control as the process of ensuring that developments are carried out as approved by local planning authorities. The term accords with the concept of quality control. Nasarawa is one of the towns in Nigeria that is faced with development control enforcement problems, which was occasioned by the increase in population due to the birth rate and immigration of people to the town. The immigration of people is attributed to the change in status of the town from the year 1984 when Federal Polytechnic Nasarawa was established. There has been an influx of people into the town for academic pursuit, business, and search for jobs and a better life. There is, therefore, high demand for the construction of more buildings and pressure on available facilities and amenities. The town is experiencing high demand and competition for several land uses, with problems such incessant waste disposal leading to blockages of drainage lines, construction on prime agricultural lands and wetlands, inadequate setbacks for buildings especially areas close to rivers resulting in floodings like the one that occurred in the year 2020 where lives and properties were destroyed it also resulted into loss in size of reserved open spaces, and haphazard development over available land.

One of the predominant problems facing our urban centres is that of promoting balanced land use and real estate planning, development, and management that reduces conflicts, danger to human health, and environmental degradation which will lead to efficiency and sustainability (Hamin, & Gurrán, 2009).

Brueckner, (2000) opined that urban lands are becoming increasingly scarce resources. The point is that a growing urban population requires land for numerous activities. On the other hand, the land is a finite resource, while the demand for land increases thereby posing

challenges to land managers and planners. It should be noted that human needs must be satisfied on the fixed land and development must be located on the limited land. Activities have to compete for the use of the best sites for their location; hence the principle of optimality has to be adhered to. It is a fact that competition would surely lead to problems or conflicts among activities.

Nigerian cities are reputed to be the dirtiest, most unsanitary, least aesthetically pleasing, and dangerously unsafe for a living (Agbola,2002). They are characterized by nonfunctioning infrastructure facilities, most poorly governed, intensively dotted with illegal structures while physical growth and development of the cities had not been properly managed or controlled, (Aluko, 2000). According to Falade (2003), land use plans for most cities often seek to make life better for the masses living in cities as a major goal, but the reality of the case is that these lofty and laudable goals are never achieved (Falade, 2003). It is within this perspective that this paper is poised to find a balance between land use and development control enforcement measures with a view of attaining a sustainable urban land management practice in Nigeria.

Development control regulates orderly planning and growth of a country, town, or city by stipulating adequate standards for all aspects of planning (Ola 2007). It is to ensure that land is properly allocated to avoid conflict and that infrastructures are available. It is the process by which planning authorities exercise the statutory duty to control all developments following the provisions of the law. The most commonly used land-use control regulations in Nigeria include; zoning/master plan, subdivision, and building regulations (Abiodun, Olaitan, & Abimbola, 2018).

Zoning is the demarcation of a city of ordinances and the establishment of regulations to govern the use of the land (Fischel, 1987). It is an attempt to organize and systematize the growth of urban areas by setting up categories, classes, or districts of land in the community, prescribing the use to which land and building may be put, and applying uniform restrictions on the shape and placement of buildings. Fekade, (2000) states that the main objectives of development control regulations are to improve efficiency, promote agglomeration benefits, specify minimum health and safety requirements and provide land for public goods and services.

South worth, & Ben-Joseph, (1995) agreed that sub-division regulations are meant to control the physical layout of new development by establishing standards such as plot size and layout, street improvement, and other requirements in more detail than the zoning plan.

Building regulations define the way new structures are to be built and the materials to be used. They may be applied to the maintenance and improvement of existing buildings. The main objective is that of securing socially acceptable minimum standards (Crowards, 1998). It is one of the most common methods of controlling land development in Nigerian cities.

Meanwhile, control means the process of exercising power over one's area of jurisdiction to check development. Development control thus means a physical planning instrument, which generally involves the regulations, retraining, and keeping in order or checking materials' change on land. Its application tends to have a negative approach to development, while at the same time, it is a creative and permissive tool for development planning. In essence, it is a strategy employed by a physical planning agency for ensuring the proper implementation of urban and rural development plans as well as regulating the flow of additions of infrastructural facilities. Moreover, it is a regulatory power exercised by planning agencies to either approve or reject a development application. It is a system by which the use of land and buildings on the land are regulated so that misuse or abuse of use and nonconforming uses are prevented or

checked.

Meeting the challenges of land use and development standards requires a mix of policies and programs that would ensure that urban land is used in the general interest of the community.

Instruments of Development Control

We have two major instruments or tools often used in the development control process. These are:

- i. *Enforcement notice: This is served on any breach of Town planning law relating to carrying out of development without planning permission or approval. It relates to illegal building, engineering, mining, change of use, and so on. This notice may be served either for demolition of such building without approval, or the restoration of an altered building, to its previous condition under section 47(1) of the urban and regional planning Decree No. 88 of 1992. Non-compliance with an enforcement order is punishable though a breach of planning law is not a criminal offence.***
- ii. *Stop work notice: According to section 53 of the urban and regional planning Decree No. 88 of 1992, a stop-work order could be issued where it appears to the control department that:***
 - (a) *An unauthorized development is being carried out or;***
 - (b) *Where development does not comply with a development permit issued by the control department. This document is used pending the service of an enforcement notice on the owner, occupier, or holder of such property. It takes an immediate effect upon the service of such property. The time frame is usually 21 days within which such development shall comply with the provisions of section 53. It shall cease to have effect if within 21 days enforcement notice is not served on its contravener***

Challenges of Development Control

Enforcing development control laws to comply with certain standards, development control regulations are faced with many hitches in Nigeria. Numerous constraints were discovered which mitigate the effects of development control measures in the study area. Lack of up-to-date land-use map to reflect the trend of development and vehicles earmarked for development control purposes. Also, the procedure for development control is not effective since it does not allow or ensure easy access to the police and/or other law enforcement agents when there is a need to respond quickly against any defiance development. Inadequate funding of the control authority. Compared to other sectors of the economy, physical planning programs suffer a lot of sets back through inadequate funding. Rather than the government at the three tiers seeing urban and regional planning activities and programs like social services, instead, they misconstrue the development control authorities and agencies to be revenue-generating units in their setting. Lack of public enlightenment programs on physical planning issues by the local authority makes members of the public "illiterate" on physical planning programs. This leads to the development of illegal structures to fulfil their selfish interest without considering the negative impact of such action. Public support is a prerequisite to successful and effective development. There is also improper or inadequate monitoring of development to ensure compliance especially in a case where a development permit is granted. The study, however,

revealed that there is a need to departmentalized, equipped, and adequately funds the Town planning unit to enable it to cope with the challenges of development control as this would lead to constant monitoring of development daily to restore the lost glory of the town

III. Methodology

This research is based on empirical data which focuses on the impact of development control enforcement on real estate development in Nasarawa town. The research is based on primary and secondary sources of data.

The primary data for this paper include the Reconnaissance survey, the primary data was collected from direct personal interviews, responses to questionnaires administered to the people and professionals in the field of planning, and related fields were utilized by town planners, architects, and estate surveyors.

The questionnaire was designed after the works of Sommer *et al* (2000); De-Araujo (2003) and Gorman (2004). In this study, information was elicited from the respondents concerning development control and real estate development. Residents were asked a “yes” or “no question and multiple-choice questions.

The oral interview was targeted at the officers of the development control office in Nasarawa. The interview was complemented with physical observations, but the questionnaire formed the major part of the data-gathering technique for this study.

For this study, Nasarawa town was stratified into (4) four electoral wards, namely: Nasarawa North, Nasarawa East, Nasarawa Central and Nasarawa Main Town (INEC Nasarawa, 2006). According to the 2006 National Population census figures. Nasarawa has a population of 56,122 people and an estimated population of 72,143 by the use of Nasarawa state population growth rate of 2.83% (2021). Abumere (1984); Fasakin (1985) and Dauda and Osita (2003) said a typical household in Nigeria comprises of (7) seven-person. Dividing 72,143 by 7 will give 10,306 households, hence the sampling frame of the study.

Sample Size

The formula given by Kothari (2004) and adopted by Bello (2009) is chosen for this study and this is written as follows:

$$n = \frac{z^2 p.q. N}{e^2 (N - 1) + z^2 .p.q}$$

Where n = Sample size

Z = Value of standard deviation at a confidence level will be taken from the table of the normal curve as 95%

p = Sample proportion (q = 1 – p) taken as 5%

N = Size of the population from the sample frame is 10,306

e = Acceptable error is taken at 0.02 for this study

Substituting the values in the formula above, the sample size is determined as 431 households.

Thus a total of 431 household heads which are in rented and owner-occupation was randomly served with questionnaires but only 399 were filled and returned which will form the frequency for result analysis.

IV. Results and Discussion

Respondents Awareness of Nasarawa Master Plan

Table 1: Respondents Awareness of Nasarawa Master Plan

Awareness	Frequency	Percentage (%)
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Aware	142	35.6
Not aware	241	60.4
Others	16	4.0
Total	399	100

Source: Field Survey, 2021

The above table revealed that the majority of the respondent was not aware of the existence of the Nasarawa Master Plan constituting about 60.4% and only 34.6% of the respondents are aware of the existence of the Nasarawa Master Plan. This makes enforcement of development control very difficult.

Routine Visitation by Development Control Unit

Table 2: Routine Visitation by Development Control Unit

Opinion	Respondent	Percentages (%)
Yes	98	24.6
No	301	75.4
Total	399	100

Source: Field Survey, 2021

From the above survey, it could be inferred that routine visitation by the development control department is too poor as only 24.6% of the respondents are in favour of the routine inspection by the development control officers.

Existence of Building Plan

Table 3: Existence of Building Plan

Opinion	Respondent	Percentages
Yes	263	65.9
No	341	24.1
Total	399	100

Source: Field Survey, 2021

From the survey in Table 3 above, only 24.1% of the sample population have no building plan but 65.9% of the respondent had their building plan.

Approval of Building Plan

Table 4: Approval of Building Plan

Opinion	Respondent	Percentages
Yes	151	37.8
No	248	62.2
Total	399	100

Source: Field Survey, 2021

From the above, only 37.8% of the respondent had their building plan approved while 62.2% had no approval of their building plan.

Time is taken for Approval of Building Plan

Table 5: Time taken for Approval of Building Plan

Variables	Respondents	Percentage
Within 1 month	28	7.0
Within 2 months	35	8.8
Within 3 months	48	12.0
Within 4 months	50	12.5
Within 5 months	60	15.0
Within 6 months	68	17.0
Within 1 year	33	8.3
> 1 year	77	19.3
Total	399	100

Source: Field Survey, 2021

From the table above, a large percentage of people pursue the approval of their building plan for more than one year.

The major tool for development control in Nasarawa town

Table 6: Major tool for development control in Nasarawa town

S/No	Opinion	Response	Percentages
1	Enforcement notice	43	10.8
2	Stop work notice	356	89.2
	Total	399	100

Source: Field Survey, 2021

From Table 6 above 89.2% of the respondents were familiar with the stop-work notice meaning that they know the meaning and only about 10.8% of the respondent say it is enforcement notice, therefore the most popular notice within Nasarawa town is the stop-work notice.

Compliance of house owners/developers to development control activities

Table 7: Compliance of house owners/developers to development control activities

Opinion	Respondents	Percentages (%)
Excellent	21	5.3
V. Good	20	5.0
Good	80	20.0
Poor	278	69.7
Total	399	100

Source: Field Survey, 2021

Table 7 above shows that 69.7% of the respondent believe that the compliance of house owners/developers is poor, while 20% says its good, 5.3% says it's excellent and 5.0% says it's very good, but the highest opinion revealed that the several compliances of people are poor i.e it means that the effort of the development control people is often frustrated by the people. Based on the differences in the ethnicity, different people with their different designs and local building materials are often seen clinching to their culture and tradition, this was more pronounced in areas like Tammah, Angwan Bai, Angwan Biri, and the Oversea area of Nasarawa town where standards like the height of the building, ventilation conveniences are not following the development control specification.

Building within the right of way of high tension cables

Table 8: Building within the right of way of high tension cables

Opinion	Respondents	Percentages (%)
Yes	71	17.8
No	328	82.2
Total	399	100

Source: Field Survey, 2021

The above table shows that some houses are built within the right of way of the high tension wire or the power line which is not acceptable and it further shows the non-compliance of people to development control where the acceptable standard is 25 meters setback both sides of the power line. The areas most affected are; Tammah, Shagari Road, Low-cost, and Students Village area.

The setback of Building to the Access Road

Table 9: Setback of Building to the Access Road

Opinion	Respondents	Percentage (%)
Excellent	10	2.5
Good	112	28
Poor	277	69.4
Total	399	100

Source: Field Survey, 2021

The above table shows that the set back of building to the access road is poor at about 69.4% of the respondent showing that the specification of the development Revealed that people build very close to the road and some others build a lot of attachment especially shops along the road in addition to the existing development and it is against the development control law.

Major Factors Responsible for Non-enforcement of Development Control in Nasarawa Town.

The following information will be integrated and coded in determining the causes of non-implementation and failure of development control in Nasarawa town.

These are;

- 1. Insufficient legal framework –(A1)**
- 2. Lack of equipment and tools –(A2)**
- 3. Inadequate skilled personnel –(A3)**
- 4. Insufficient organizational structure for implementing development control–(A4)**
- 5. Infiltration of corrupt and compromising officials –(A5).**
- 6. Lack of data and information for decision making –(A6)**
- 7. Absence of public enlightenment on the importance of development control –(A7)**
- 8. Noninvolvement of other urban management organizations for preparing urban plan –(A8).**
- 9. Unsuitable organizational structure for implementing the urban plans –(A9).**
- 10. Insufficient financial capability –(A10).**

Table 10: Development Control Enforcement Problem in Nasarawa town

S/No	Development Control Problems Coding.	5	4	3	2	1	Mean	Ranking
1.	A1	132	143	80	30	14	3.87	8
		33.1	35.8	20.1	7.5	2.5		
2.	A2	200	123	50	20	6	4.21	4
		50.1	30.8	12.5	5.0	1.5		
3.	A3	210	112	36	21	20	4.18	6
		52.6	28.1	9.0	5.3	5.0		
4.	A4	249	66	43	19	22	4.26	3
		62.4	16.5	10.8	4.8	5.5		
5.	A5	346	30	10	12	1	4.77	1
		86.7	7.5	2.5	3.0	0.3		
6.	A6	248	72	13	40	26	4.19	5
		62.2	18.0	3.3	10.1	6.5		
7.	A7	261	51	48	29	10	4.31	2
		65.4	12.8	12.0	7.3	2.5		
8.	A8	139	117	63	44	36	3.70	9
		34.8	29.3	15.8	11.0	9.0		
9.	A9	112	74	131	15	67	3.37	10
		28.0	18.5	32.8	3.8	16.8		
10.	A10	221	27	116	12	23	4.00	7
		55.4	6.8	29.1	3.0	5.8		

Source: Field Survey, 2021

The above table revealed that several problems are associated with the enforcement of development control in Nasarawa town as analyzed in the table coded as (A1, A2...A10). The problems were ranked following the mean score and the three (3) top ranking are: - A5, A7, and A4 respectively.

- A5: Infiltration of corrupt and compromising officers***
- A7: Absence of public enlightenment on the importance of development control enforcement.***
- A4: Insufficient organizational structure for implementing development control enforcement.***

Relationship between Development Control and Real Estate in Nasarawa Town
Table 11: Relationship between Development Control Enforcement and Real Estate

S/No	Variables	5	4	3	2	1	Mean	Ranking
1.	Orderly environment	122	82	88	77	30	3.47	4
		30.6	20.6	22.1	19.3	7.5		
2.	It promotes hygiene and good health	136	96	30	60	77	3.39	5
		34.1	24.1	7.5	15.0	19.3		
3.	It creates sound access and a good drainage system	100	140	25	80	54	3.38	6
		25.1	35.1	6.27	20.1	13.5		
4.	It enhances the value of	186	120	20	50	23	3.99	1
						3		

	the real estate	46.6	30.1	50.0	12.5	5.8		
5.	It encourages developers to build in the area	150	113	60	50	26	3.78	2
		37.5	28.3	15.0	12.5	6.52		
		9	2	4	3			
6	It brings about a sustainable real estate development	183	71	55	50	40	3.77	3
		45.8	17.8	13.8	12.5	10.0		

Source: Field Survey, 2021

The above table revealed among other variables that the top three (3) rankings of the relationship between development control and real estate are as follows.

- 1. It enhances the value of the real estate**
- 2. It encourages developers to build in the area**
- 3. It brings about a sustainable real estate development**

Summary of Findings Conclusion and Recommendations

The followings are the summary of constraints of development control in Nasarawa town;

- ***Infiltration of corrupt and compromising officers***
- ***Lack of up-to-date land-use map to reflect the trend of development and vehicles earmarked for development control purposes. Also, the procedure for development control is not effective since it does not allow or ensure easy access to the police and/or other law enforcement agents when there is a need to respond quickly against any defiance development.***
- ***Lack of public enlightenment programs on physical planning makes members of the public "illiterate" on physical planning programs. This leads to the development of illegal structures to fulfil their selfish interest without considering the negative impact of such action.***
- ***There is also improper or inadequate monitoring of development to ensure compliance especially in a case where a development permit (approval) is granted.***
- ***Inadequacy of professionally qualified town planners in the Town planning unit of the authority.***
- ***The followings are the recommendations;***
- ***Strict enforcement of the control laws and regulations enforced.***
- ***Officers should ensure that undue excuses, delays, and corruption should be avoided as much as possible.***
- ***Urban and regional planning Decrees 88 of 1992 should be put to test to ascertain the effectiveness of the law.***
- ***New and relevant, bye-laws, edicts, acts, and regulations mitigate development control challenges should be introduced.***
- ***The Nasarawa Geographical Information System (NAGIS) should be extended to the local governments to further monitor land use and management.***
- ***Adequate funding of the development control unit should be given adequate attention.***

- ***Illegal subdivision of plot and designated spaces must be completely disallowed by inhabitants/property owners to prevent congestion and overcrowding.***

Conclusion

There will be new development originating from urbanization and economic fortune. For a development control exercise to be successful new ideas that will meet current and future needs must be integrated into their operation. To preserve already planned settlement and guide against others developing into a slum. The development control unit must be accorded its rightful place in areas of planning.

Finally, emphasis should also be given to translating policies into action. There are many good policies in Nigeria but they are not being implemented. For example, the urban and regional planning law created Planning agencies at federal, state, and local levels, but this has not yet been translated into action. Likewise, the Land Commission established in 2001 to address the land issue is not yet functioning.

To remove the gaps between policies and practice provision should be made for participatory monitoring and evaluation of the policies, along with room for necessary adjustments.

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